

COMMUNITY-BASED STRATEGIES FOR CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION AND RESILIENCE IN ASANTE MAMPONG, GHANA

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Abstract

Various communities around the world have implemented successful climate resilience and adaptation strategies. For instance, communities along the Nile River have adopted floodplain farming practices, while Australian Aboriginal communities have been using traditional fire management techniques. Ethiopian pastoralist communities have developed strategies such as herd splitting, mobility patterns, and diversified livelihoods to manage drought. Traditional irrigation techniques are utilized in the arid regions of Kenya, and water harvesting techniques are employed in the semi-arid regions of Brazil. Additionally, green roofs have been planted on buildings in Stuttgart, Germany. Other effective strategies have been observed in Phoenix in Arizona, Costa Rica, Nepal, Bangladesh, and among Malawian and Ghanaian farmers. These indigenous groups have established intricate adaptation plans through community-led risk assessments, planning, and disaster recovery, promoting knowledge-sharing and collaboration across all levels. They have employed flexible and context-specific adaptation policies, grassroots coping mechanisms, including physical, economic, and social means, and culturally sensitive and participatory decision-making support tools. The creation of community resilience frameworks that center on economic development, social capital, information and communication, and community competence has helped enhance resilience to climate-related stressors.

Key Words: Asante Mampong, Ghana, Climate Adaptation, Climate Resilience

1.1 Introduction

Community resilience strategies in the face of climate change involve various approaches, such as the implementation of programs like Climate Village (Kampung Iklim) and the integration of innovative smart village concepts from smart cities and communities (Ariyaningsih, 2023). Indigenous groups have established intricate adaptation plans through community-led risk assessments, planning, and disaster recovery, promoting knowledge-sharing and collaboration across all levels (Carlos, 2023). These communities have employed flexible and context-specific adaptation policies (Boswell, 2012), grassroots coping mechanisms, including physical, economic, and social means (Jabeen, 2010), and culturally sensitive and participatory decision-making support tools (Nkoana, 2018). Furthermore, the creation of community resilience frameworks that center on economic development, social capital, information and communication, and community competence has helped enhance resilience to climate-related stressors (Bajayo, 2012).

Several key strategies can help enhance the effectiveness of resilience strategies at the individual, community, and government levels. These include community preparedness, which involves conducting needs-based assessments, engaging with the community, and fostering ongoing collaboration. It is also important to establish frameworks that are regularly monitored, evaluated, and promoted, as this can help ensure that resilience efforts remain effective over time (Shona et al., 2022). To assess social vulnerability and community resilience, multi-criteria decision analysis can be used to identify influential macro-indicators and areas in need of attention. This information can be invaluable for decision-makers who are looking to adopt and implement effective preventive measures (Antronico et al., 2023). At the local level, managed retreats, for example, can help reduce the social and economic costs of climate-related disasters. Meanwhile, water-saving irrigation practices can contribute to water security in the face of droughts. Early warning

systems can also be incredibly valuable, as they can empower communities to take preventative measures and protect their lives and livelihoods during extreme weather events.

1.2 Global Case Studies and Local Strategies

The impact of climate change presents a significant risk to communities worldwide, necessitating adaptation to changing environments. Numerous studies have recognized successful strategies leveraged by various communities globally to build resilience against climate-related challenges. In the United States, Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) connects customers with local farmers, promoting sustainable agriculture and increasing access to fresh, locally-produced food (Guthman, 2000). In Phoenix, Arizona, implementing strategies like planting heat-resistant trees, creating cool pavements, and establishing cooling centers has been successful in combating extreme heat (Hoffman et al., 2020). In the Arctic, investing in relocating critical infrastructure, emergency preparedness planning, and the recovery of vital activities ensures sustained livability and builds community resilience to climate-related disasters (Taarup-Esbensen, 2022). In semi-arid regions of Brazil, communities have adopted water harvesting techniques like cisterns to capture and store rainwater for household use during dry periods (Silva et al., 2012). The Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) programs in Costa Rica provide financial incentives to landowners for protecting forests, conserving biodiversity, and mitigating climate change impacts (Wunder et al., 2008).

In Europe, cities like Stuttgart in Germany have adopted green roofs on buildings to combat urban heat island effects, manage stormwater runoff, and enhance air quality (Berndt et al., 2009). The Netherlands has a rich heritage of managing rising sea levels through strategies such as dikes, levees, and land elevation projects (Klijn et al., 2019). Australian Aboriginal communities have been utilizing traditional fire management techniques for centuries, which can effectively reduce

the risk of large, uncontrollable wildfires (Jackson et al., 2019). Incorporating cyclone-resistant features in building codes has been a successful approach in Australia to minimize storm damage. Climate change-induced extreme weather events pose a significant threat to the Himalayas. In Nepal, local communities have taken proactive measures to minimize casualties and damages caused by floods and landslides by implementing early warning systems through local communication networks (Bajracharya et al., 2017). As a result of rising sea levels due to climate change, coastal communities in Bangladesh have successfully adopted the strategy of "managed retreat," relocating homes and infrastructure further inland to protect against storm surges and flooding (Rahman et al., 2020). In arid regions of Kenya, traditional irrigation techniques have been employed for centuries to conserve water and adapt to drought conditions (Nyong'a et al., 2011). Ethiopian pastoralist communities have developed traditional strategies such as herd splitting, mobility patterns, and diversified livelihoods to manage drought (Desta & Coppock, 2004). Communities along the Nile River have adapted to seasonal flooding through floodplain farming practices that utilize floodwaters for agriculture (Eriksen et al., 2005). In Southern Africa, Malawian farmers can purchase index-based insurance that provides payouts based on rainfall data, helping to manage drought risk (Cole et al., 2013). Senegal has also developed climate-resilient seed varieties for crops like millet and sorghum, which can help farmers adapt to changing weather patterns (Traore et al., 2013).

Ghana has proactively developed a comprehensive National Adaptation Plan (NAP) that thoughtfully addresses climate change across a variety of sectors, including agriculture, water resources, and human health. By reviewing this plan, one can gain valuable insight into the innovative strategies already in place or being considered in Ghana. Northern Ghana, in particular, is at risk of land degradation due to climate change. However, communities in the region have

taken steps to protect their soil and water resources by implementing hillside terracing and improved drainage systems (Baaffour et al., 2017). To help prevent potential flooding, the Ghana Meteorological Agency has created early warning systems in flood-prone areas that utilize text messages, radio broadcasts, and community sirens to alert residents (World Bank, 2016). Additionally, Ghanaian farmers have embraced Farmer Managed Natural Regeneration (FMNR) as a technique to promote biodiversity, improve soil fertility, and mitigate climate change impacts by encouraging the regrowth of trees on their land (Dugbey et al., 2018).

1.3 The Challenge of Building Community Resilience

While the case studies presented offer valuable insights, it is crucial to acknowledge the complexities involved in building and enhancing community resilience. The success of these strategies depends on various factors, and there are significant challenges that need to be addressed (Magin et al., 2014). One of the major hurdles is securing access to resources. Implementing adaptation strategies, such as constructing sea walls or early warning systems, often requires substantial financial investment (Agrawal, 2008; Schipper and Langston, 2015). Communities, particularly those in developing regions, may struggle to secure the necessary funding to implement these large-scale projects. Another challenge lies in building technical expertise within the community (Yousuf et al., 2020). Successful adaptation strategies may require specific knowledge and skills for implementation and maintenance. A lack of awareness or training among community members can impede the adoption and effectiveness of these practices (Adger et al., 2005; Nhamo et al., 2020). Furthermore, top-down approaches to adaptation, where solutions are imposed without considering local contexts and needs, are often met with resistance and ultimately prove less effective (Agrawal & Gupta, 2000). Successful adaptation strategies require a

participatory approach that engages the community in decision-making processes and leverages their local knowledge and experiences (Castleden et al., 2014).

1.4 Objectives of Study

1. To identify existing community-based strategies in Asante Mampong for adapting to the specific effects of climate change
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of these local community resilience strategies in improving the community's ability to adapt to climate change
3. To investigate any social, economic, and environmental challenges that hinder the implementation and effectiveness of community resilience strategies in Asante Mampong.

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Asset-Based Approach

This research adopts the asset-based approach as a theoretical framework to investigate climate change adaptation strategies in Asante Mampong, Ghana. This approach emphasizes understanding and building upon a community's existing strengths and resources, rather than solely focusing on vulnerabilities and deficits (Kahn & Sylvest, 2020). In the context of climate change adaptation, this framework acknowledges that communities possess valuable knowledge, practices, and social networks that can be leveraged to enhance their resilience.

The asset-based approach is directly aligned with the research objectives. The first objective is to identify local community resilience strategies. This involves exploring the coping mechanisms and perceptions of the Asante Mampong community to determine the strategies they have developed to deal with climate change impacts. These could include traditional knowledge about weather patterns (Mahlangu & Ntshangase, 2017), resource management practices for water scarcity (Nyong & Pelling, 2015), or social networks (Adger et al., 2009) for support during extreme

weather events. The second objective evaluates the impact of these strategies on climate change adaptation. It analyzes how these strategies address specific challenges and contribute to the community's ability to recover from climate shocks. Lastly, it investigates challenges to community resilience. The study acknowledges that communities face limitations in their capacity to adapt, and explores challenges related to limited resources, access to information, or institutional barriers (Kahn & Sylvest, 2020).

The Asset-Based Approach offers numerous benefits, including community empowerment. This approach places communities as active participants in shaping their resilience, encouraging a sense of ownership, and promoting sustainable solutions (Wallerstein & Wejnert, 2023). Additionally, this approach allows for the identification of culturally appropriate interventions by recognizing the community's existing strengths and challenges (Lenihan & Lister, 2016). By building upon local strategies, this research informs the development of interventions that align with the community's context (Mabele & Makaudze, 2022). With a focus on existing assets, this approach can lead to the creation of sustainable adaptation strategies that have a higher likelihood of long-term success (Juhola et al., 2019). Ultimately, the asset-based approach provides a valuable framework for examining climate change adaptation in Asante Mampong. By highlighting the community's strengths and existing strategies, this research can generate insights that empower residents and inform the development of effective and sustainable adaptation strategies.

3.1 Methods

3.1.1 Study Area

This research was conducted in Asante Mampong, a municipality in Ghana's Ashanti Region. As of 2021, the population of the area was 191,402, with a population density of 7,918 people per square kilometer spread across a total land area of 24.17 square kilometers (Ghana Statistical

Service, 2021). The community experienced a negative population growth rate of -4.2% between 2010 and 2021 (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021). As of 2021, the gender ratio was nearly equal, with 93,506 men and 97,896 women (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021). Asante Mampong experiences a humid subtropical climate characterized by moderate temperatures and distinct wet and dry seasons (Peel et al., 2007). The presence of forests within the mountainous landscape (Environmental Protection Agency, Ghana [EPA], 2022) suggests a microclimate with potentially higher rainfall compared to surrounding areas. Agriculture is the primary economic driver in the area, with a majority of the population engaged in farming (Messean et al., 2017). Cash crops like cocoa and food crops such as yams and various vegetables are significant contributors to the local economy. Women in the community play a vital role in the local economy by participating in petty trading and selling agricultural produce or other goods and services in the market area and along the streets of the main station.

3.1.2 Research Approach

A qualitative research approach was employed to gain in-depth insights into the knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, and experiences of community members regarding climate change and community resilience (Edward & Tsang, 2023). This research approach offered the potential to understand the lived experiences and perceptions of the study participants on climate change and community resilience, using approaches such as key informant interviews (Suada et al., 2023) and participatory rural appraisal (Papakitsou, 2020).

3.1.3 Data Collection and Analysis

A purposive sampling technique was used to select six (6) key informants for the study. This technique ensures participants have relevant knowledge and experience with the research topic (Polit & Beck, 2017). Research participants included local farmers, a community leader, a

traditional authority, and a representative from the community's youth coalition – all of whom play crucial roles in community resilience efforts. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the selected participants. The interview guide explored themes like personal experiences with climate change impacts on livelihoods and the environment, existing community strategies for coping with these challenges, perspectives on how to strengthen community resilience, and challenges in community resilience. Additionally, field diaries were used to document observations and contextual details during fieldwork. Throughout the research process, informed consent was obtained from all participants. Participation was voluntary and anonymity was assured to protect participants from any potential physical, emotional, or psychological harm. Thematic data analysis was employed to identify recurring themes and patterns within the collected interview data and field notes. This analysis helps to understand the shared experiences, perceptions, and concerns of community members in Asante Mampong regarding climate change and community resilience.

4.1 Presentation and Analysis of Data

4.1.1 Analysis of Demographic Data

This study involved a total of six participants, with three (3) females and three (3) males, ranging in age from 32 to 75. Two (2) participants completed junior high school, three (3) completed senior high school, and one (1) finished elementary school. Of the six (6) participants, four (4) were married, one (1) was separated, and one (1) was single. The majority of the male participants work in farming, a major industry in the local villages, while the females engage primarily in minor trading at the market and main station.

4.1.2 Community-Based Strategies for Adapting to the Specific Effects of Climate Change

This section analyzes how the community copes with climate change. The findings reveal a transition from government aid to community-based adaptation.

4.1.2.1 Traditional Reliance on Government Agencies

The findings highlight the community's historical dependence on government intervention, particularly from the National Disaster Management Organization (NADMO), during extreme weather events. A participant's exemplifies this reliance.

"We typically rely on the government for assistance during extreme weather conditions..."

This observed behavior aligns with existing research by Neria et al. (2020) who emphasize the critical role of government support in disaster response efforts. However, this reliance on external aid also raises potential implications for the community's long-term resilience. Overdependence on external support could limit the community's ability to develop and implement its own disaster preparedness and response strategies (Wisner et al., 2020). This could lead to a reactive approach, waiting for government intervention rather than proactively taking steps to mitigate risks (Neria et al., 2020). Depending solely on government intervention in times of disaster may result in delays in receiving essential aid. The bureaucracy and resource constraints at the government level could impede prompt responses, particularly in the immediate aftermath of an event. Moreover, the long-term viability of this model is debatable. Government resources may not always be readily available, and funding priorities could shift, leaving the community vulnerable if external support dwindles. Recent research by Neria et al. (2020) and Alsop et al. (2020) suggests a growing recognition of the limitations of top-down disaster management approaches. Their works highlight a shift in power dynamics, with communities increasingly demanding greater participation in decision-making processes concerning disaster preparedness and response.

4.1.2.2 A Shift Towards Community-Based Solutions

While the findings confirm a historical reliance on government intervention (see Section 4.2.1), they also uncover a significant shift in attitudes. Participant narratives express a growing awareness of the limitations of solely relying on external assistance.

"...it might be worth considering community-based climate adaptation strategies.... I believe apart from relying on the government, the community members can adopt their community-led climate resilience strategies "

These observations suggest a positive development within the community. Residents are demonstrating a growing sense of agency and a desire for proactive adaptation. This shift towards community-based solutions aligns with current research on climate change adaptation (Agrawal, 2020; McGregor and Lawson, 2022; Reid et al., 2021) which emphasizes the critical role of local knowledge and participation. The potential benefits of community-based solutions are enormous. Community-driven solutions can foster a greater sense of ownership and responsibility for disaster preparedness and response. This can lead to increased community buy-in and sustainability of adaptation efforts (Agrawal, 2008; Sultana, 2010). Local communities possess unique knowledge of their environment and vulnerabilities. Community-based solutions can be tailored to address specific local challenges more effectively than broader government initiatives (Mahimwalla et al., 2019; Reid et al., 2016). The process of developing and implementing community-based solutions can empower residents and build local capacity for disaster preparedness and response. This can lead to a more resilient community in the long term (Cutter et al., 2016; Juhola et al., 2019).

4.1.2.3 The Role of Infrastructure

The research highlights the critical role of infrastructure in mitigating the impacts of extreme weather events. This aligns with established research emphasizing the importance of disaster risk reduction (DRR) strategies, particularly investments in appropriate infrastructure (United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction [UNISDR], 2017). Effective drainage systems, as

mentioned by a resident, exemplify such infrastructure, acting as a first line of defense by reducing flood severity and protecting lives and property (Koksal & Yalcin, 2015).

"About years ago, there was a heavy downpour...we were lucky we have big gutters here. If not for the gutters, the worst would have happened..."

The findings emphasize infrastructure as a key to disaster risk reduction. The firsthand account of the flooding event highlights the significance of drainage systems in mitigating the impact of disasters by effectively directing surplus water away from inhabited zones (Koksal & Yalcin, 2015). Adequate infrastructure, including properly maintained drainage systems and flood barriers, can serve as a protective shield, shielding both lives and property from the devastating effects of floods and other severe weather occurrences (United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction [UNISDR], 2015).

4.1.2.4 Support from Religious Bodies

In climate-related emergencies, religious organizations, such as the Church of Pentecost, serve as vital community support networks. Their proactive involvement indicates that religious institutions can make a substantial contribution to community resilience and disaster response efforts.

4.1.2.4.1 Diverse Forms of Support

According to the findings, the Church of Pentecost has emerged as a prominent supporter of communities during climate-related emergencies. This finding is consistent with a growing body of research highlighting the valuable role of faith-based organizations (FBOs) in climate change adaptation (Feinberg et al., 2020). FBOs have a deep understanding of local contexts and possess strong social networks within the community (Hauer et al., 2013), enabling them to offer a range of vital support services during times of crisis. Some examples of support services provided by FBOs include material aid distribution, such as the distribution of "foodstuffs and dry clothing" to

meet basic needs for food, water, clothing, and hygiene products during disasters (Hauer et al., 2013). FBOs can also offer financial assistance for basic needs like food, shelter, and medical care, helping to alleviate some of the financial burdens faced by those impacted by climate disasters (DeWaal & Ferguson, 2014). Additionally, FBOs can mobilize volunteers and resources for critical tasks, such as rebuilding efforts after disasters (Alvord et al., 2006). Furthermore, FBOs can provide psycho-social support to those affected by climate disasters in the form of spiritual guidance, emotional support, and counseling (Aldrigue & Marín, 2010).

4.1.2.4.2 Strengths of Religious Organizations

Numerous studies have emphasized the indispensable role of religious organizations in providing emotional support and counseling to those affected by climate disasters (Aldrigue & Marín, 2010). By fostering a sense of belonging, solidarity, and comfort, religious organizations enhance social cohesion and trust within communities (Feinberg et al., 2020). Moreover, religious organizations can serve as bridges between different groups, promoting social inclusion and ensuring that everyone has access to support (Aldrich & Beckett, 2009). Due to their extensive networks and infrastructure, religious organizations can quickly and efficiently mobilize aid and relief efforts (Hauer et al., 2013). They often enlist and educate volunteers from their congregations to participate in relief work, and this volunteer force plays a critical role in disaster response and recovery efforts (Alvord et al., 2006). Additionally, many religious organizations actively support policies that aim to mitigate the effects of climate change and raise public awareness of these impacts (Feinberg et al., 2020). Through programs and initiatives, religious organizations also empower their communities to prepare for climate-related disasters, including conducting drills, developing emergency plans, and promoting overall community preparedness (Feinberg et al., 2020).

4.1.2.5 Cultural Explanations for Disasters

Understanding how communities perceive and respond to disasters requires acknowledging the influence of cultural beliefs and practices. One of the participants describes a horrible situation involving a pastor and his family. In this case, when his wife was away, a house fire claimed the life of the pastor along with his three children. Notably, the doors were locked during the incident, making escape impossible.

"A recent fire incident claimed the lives of a pastor, his three children, and an old woman in their home. The cause of the fire remains unknown. Notably, after the incident, it was observed that all the doors were locked from the inside, hindering escape... "

Additionally, the participant states that locals thought this catastrophe was caused by African magic, which may indicate a cultural belief in supernatural origins. While the incident cannot, in itself, be attributed solely to any specific belief, it raises the possibility that some community members might interpret and react to disasters through the lens of cultural explanations. People's cultural beliefs can shape their understanding of disasters, potentially impacting preparedness and response behaviors (Nygren et al., 2019)

"...this event sparked discussions within the community, with some attributing it to supernatural causes. Locals claimed the pastor might have offended someone who sought to harm him and his extended family."

Disaster response strategies must be culturally sensitive, acknowledging the role of local beliefs and practices (Maskrey, 1998). Effective disaster management requires collaboration and mutual understanding between practitioners, researchers, and community members (Gaillard, 2009). This includes engaging with community leaders, faith-based organizations, and individuals to comprehend cultural influences on preparedness and response. Understanding cultural beliefs allows for the development of culturally appropriate communication materials and educational

programs (Shaw, 2009). These resources can resonate with community members and promote effective risk mitigation strategies.

4.1.2.6 Community Mobilization

This subsection delves deeper into the theme of community mobilization in Asante Mampong, with a specific focus on the crucial role played by the youth. Drawing upon participant reports, the analysis highlights the proactive engagement of young people in addressing local challenges arising from climate-related disasters and road infrastructure issues.

4.1.2.6.1 Grassroots Initiatives and Active Citizenship

The findings emphasize a grassroots approach adopted by the youth in Asante Mampong. Participant narratives depict young people taking the initiative to gather sand and fill potholes created by heavy rainfall or general road wear and tear.

"...In the aftermath of climate-induced disasters that damage road infrastructure, young men in the community take the initiative to repair the potholes. They gather loose sand from other locations and utilize it to fill the holes on the road."

This exemplifies their sense of ownership and responsibility towards the community's well-being. It signifies a form of active citizenship where young people are not merely passive recipients of aid, but rather active contributors to solutions (Reid et al., 2021).

4.1.2.6.2 Strengthening Social Cohesion and Resilience

Community mobilization fosters problem-solving capacities within the community. Young people take the initiative to address local challenges without solely relying on external resources or intervention from government agencies. This fosters a sense of self-reliance and empowers the community to take charge of its well-being (Nadasen and Gonçalves, 2023).

"When the storm hit the village last year, it tore away many roofs. But despite the damage, nobody had to go hungry because we all worked together. The younger members of the community helped the older ones fix their roofs with whatever materials they could find, and we shared whatever food we had left. We understood that if we didn't collaborate, the situation would have been much worse. This is how we have always done things in our village - by taking care of each other."

In addition, working together on these initiatives strengthens social networks and support systems within the community. Collaborative efforts in pothole repair likely involve communication, coordination, and potentially even knowledge sharing amongst the youth. This fosters a sense of unity and collective responsibility, crucial for building community resilience in the face of climate-related disasters (Nyong'a et al., 2018).

4.1.2.6.3 Challenging Stereotypes and Reframing Youth Agency

The findings extend beyond considerations of infrastructure and community-based solutions. They also challenge stereotypical perceptions of youth as passive recipients of aid. Participant narratives highlight the potential of young people in the community to be active contributors to solutions.

One quote exemplifies this point:

"Young people often receive unfair criticism, but during the recent floods, it was the young adults who bravely waded through the chest-high water to retrieve medicine for sick individuals who were unable to leave their homes. These young ones are not afraid of hard work, they simply require an opportunity to showcase their abilities."

This statement demonstrates the proactive role young people can play in addressing community challenges. Their courage and willingness to take action during the flood incident dispel stereotypes of youth as apathetic or incapable. This aligns with the growing body of research that emphasizes youth agency and their potential to be significant actors in climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction efforts (Castrilli et al., 2019). By recognizing and empowering young people in Asante Mampong, the community can unlock a valuable resource for building resilience.

4.1.3 Effectiveness of the Community-Based Resilience Strategies in Improving the Community's Ability to Adapt to Climate Change

4.1.3.1 Community Policies and Public Services

In response to the challenges posed by climate change, the Asante Mampong community exhibits a noteworthy shift in focus towards public health, social services, and responsible behavior. Participant narratives reveal a growing awareness of the importance of medical care, health education, and social support in the aftermath of climate-related disasters. This proactive approach aligns with research on community-based adaptation, where local knowledge and capacity are crucial for building resilience (Adger et al., 2005, 2008; Neria et al., 2017).

“Our attention has now focused on public health and social services in response to climate change-related events. For instance, we are working toward an increase in health awareness programs and access to medical facilities. We always ensure that we quickly clean up the areas and that affected residents receive prompt medical attention and social services”

“While our community may lack well-equipped health centers and regular health education programs, there is a growing awareness of how burning agricultural waste contributes to air pollution and climate change. This growing consciousness highlights our potential to adapt and contribute to positive environmental change, even with limited resources”

The community's prioritization of improved access to medical facilities, health awareness campaigns, and rapid response efforts for clean-up demonstrates a clear understanding of the health risks associated with climate change (Watts et al., 2018). Additionally, despite the limitations of well-equipped health centers and regular health education programs, residents demonstrate a growing awareness of how burning agricultural waste contributes to air pollution and climate change. This highlights the community's potential to adapt, even with limited resources (Neria et al., 2017). This suggests a potential for adaptation and a willingness to adopt more responsible practices, such as reducing agricultural waste burning. These findings have significant implications for building long-term resilience. The community's focus on public health, social services, and

responsible behavior can inform policymakers and resource allocation strategies (Mustefa et al., 2023).

4.1.3.2 Community-Driven Strategies and Policy Influence

The findings explore the significant role of community-driven initiatives in influencing government policies related to climate change adaptation. Participant narratives highlight how community involvement can lead to positive changes in infrastructure and regulations that ultimately enhance resilience. The report emphasizes the importance of local projects, particularly those undertaken by the youth, such as drainage maintenance (Reid et al., 2016). A participant highlights how these initiatives have fostered closer collaboration between the community and the government in developing climate change policies. This collaboration is further evidenced by recent infrastructure upgrades, such as the installation of larger gutters and road improvements

“.... Again, our local initiatives, such as drainage maintenance which is mostly ensured by our youth have prompted the government to collaborate with us more closely and consider our input when formulating climate change policies. This is evident in the big gutters and the tarred road you see around. They are all recent changes”

The reported closer collaboration between the community and the government in developing climate change policies signifies a positive outcome of community-driven efforts. This collaboration is further evidenced by recent infrastructure upgrades, such as the installation of larger gutters and road improvements, which directly address community vulnerabilities.

This suggests that community-driven strategies can act as a catalyst for positive change. By demonstrating local knowledge and a willingness to take action, communities can influence government policies toward more effective adaptation strategies (Mustefa et al., 2023).

Furthermore, research suggests that fostering social capital and collective action within communities strengthens their ability to advocate for policy changes that support adaptation efforts

(Adger et al., 2005). Additionally, studies have shown that effective communication and collaboration between communities and policymakers are essential for translating local knowledge and needs into implementable adaptation policies (Nygren et al., 2019). A recent study in Nepal found that community-led initiatives, such as rainwater harvesting and flood protection measures, demonstrably influenced government policies towards allocating resources for decentralized adaptation projects (Chapagain & Hajer, 2015). It is important to acknowledge that sustaining community-driven adaptation efforts requires ongoing support and capacity building. This can include providing training, resources, and access to technical expertise to empower communities for long-term resilience (Mahimwalla et al., 2019).

4.1.4 The Challenges to Effective Community-Based Resilience Strategies

4.1.4.1 Limited Opportunities and Stagnant Development

Participant narratives consistently highlight the limited employment opportunities available to young people in the community. They reveal a restricted job market, with driving and small businesses being the primary sources of income for young people. This lack of alternative career paths is a considerable barrier to a thriving youth population. Youths' experiences of being "idle" or "walking around" due to a lack of jobs, as expressed in the participants' report, highlight a sense of stagnation and unrealized potential.

"...and for our youth, apart from driving and keeping shops, they do not have any better jobs. Someone has to open a shop and employ them."

"As for the youth, they are just walking around in town all day and night. They don't have any reliable jobs"

"... Another problem is unemployment. We do not have enough government work here. Most of the youth here engage in casual work, especially construction work. They are masons, or drivers, or shopkeepers. You will always see them walking around during the day"

These findings align with previous research on the detrimental effects of youth unemployment on both social and economic factors. Sherrieb et al. (2010) found that limited job opportunities can

lead to increased anxiety among young people, which can negatively impact community well-being and even foster social unrest. The International Labour Organization (2020) has also emphasized the far-reaching developmental consequences of youth unemployment. In their 2020 World Employment and Social Outlook report, the ILO highlights the correlation between youth unemployment and reduced economic growth, innovation, and social instability (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2020). The challenges faced by youth in Asante Mampong are not unique, as a 2021 study by the African Development Bank (AfDB) revealed similar obstacles in rural African communities. The report cited a lack of skills development programs and limited access to financing as significant barriers for young entrepreneurs (African Development Bank [AfDB], 2021).

4.1.4.2 Environmental Changes

The Asante Mampong community has noticed major environmental changes, especially those connected to changes in the weather and climatic conditions. Participant narratives highlight a growing awareness of shifts in weather patterns and an increase in colder temperatures, particularly at night during specific months. While flooding is not mentioned as a frequent concern, participants consistently report experiencing unusual cold spells, especially in December. This perception of a changing climate is further supported by comments about less intense sunshine and the need for additional protection from the cold.

“I have lived in this community for more than 20 years, and there have been noticeable changes in the climate, recently. The weather has been colder during certain months, particularly in the evenings. It was not like that during my childhood”.

Other participants emphasized how uncommon it is compared to prior experiences that Mampong has become substantially cooler, particularly on the nights around December. Their comment implies that locals are becoming more conscious of changes in weather patterns.

"I have strong ties to this community and have observed changes in the weather and climate over time. Mampong has notably become colder, particularly during December evenings, which is quite unusual. It is evident that weather patterns are shifting."

"The sun rarely shines these days, and the weather has changed significantly. It is not advisable to remain outside for extended periods, especially in December, unless you want to risk freezing to death. This has become a common occurrence in Mampong, which is a mountainous community. Frequent rainfalls and low temperatures make the area cold almost all the time."

Although flooding is not commonly discussed, the recent emphasis on colder temperatures highlights how climate change can affect regions differently. The community's understanding aligns with Ghana's projected climate trends, as outlined in The Fourth National Communication of Ghana under the UNFCCC (2024) and the National Adaptation Plan Project by the Environmental Protection Agency of Ghana (2024), which predicts an increase in mean temperatures. However, the occurrence of colder nights in the local area suggests that there may be microclimatic variations or specific weather events at play (Brown, 2014; Elmqvist et al., 2019). To foster long-term resilience, the community may need to adapt its strategies to address a wider range of climate threats. This could involve creating new coping mechanisms for colder temperatures, reassessing existing preparedness plans, and investing in infrastructure that is climate-resilient and can endure a wider range of environmental stresses (Agrawal, 2008).

4.1.4.3 Flooding

Flooding in Asante Mampong presents a complex challenge, with both historical and contemporary dimensions. While some residents downplay flooding as a regular event, a harrowing account serves as a stark reminder of its potential devastation. A past incident resulted in the tragic loss of life, highlighting the catastrophic potential of major floods. However, the absence of similar events in recent years suggests a possible decline in their frequency.

"...rising water levels submerged the entire road, obscuring gutters and tragically resulting in the loss of life for a family of three who were caught in the floodwaters."

Fortunately, such extreme flooding events have not been reported in the community for the past four years.”

The Tadeam River is identified as a primary source of flooding. Unexpected overflows, particularly at night, cause significant disruption and damage to local businesses, underlining the negative economic impact. Participant narratives illustrate this concern:

“Flooding in our community is primarily caused by the Tadeam River behind the market. This river tends to flood unexpectedly, often at night, causing damage to people's businesses.”

There is growing concern about how urban development may worsen flooding. The recent sighting of a construction project encroaching on a waterway underscores the critical importance of including flood risk assessments in urban planning strategies. This emphasizes the urgent need for more stringent regulations on development in floodplains to avoid exacerbating existing flooding issues.

“...construction work is currently ongoing at the KIA station, just behind the market. You won't believe it, but they are building on a waterway. The plan is to rent out the shops they are building to market women. Because they needed it to be close to the market, they didn't consider the fact that they were building on a waterway. Unfortunately, this is also causing flooding in the area. Additionally, SSNIT (Social Security and National Insurance Trust) is building a huge office on the same waterway, which is exacerbating the problem.”

Although Asante Mampong has experienced fewer instances of flooding in recent years, it is still important to recognize and address potential risks. Employing a multi-faceted approach is crucial to effective management, taking into account both natural and human-induced factors. Firstly, implementing improved flood forecasting and early warning systems can empower residents to take preventative measures and minimize potential damage (Krebs et al., 2017). Secondly, investing in green infrastructure solutions, such as natural waterways and retention ponds, can regulate stormwater runoff and reduce flood risks (Fletcher et al., 2015). Thirdly, implementing stricter regulations on development in floodplains can prevent construction that could obstruct

waterways and exacerbate flooding issues (WMO, 2017). Finally, developing comprehensive community preparedness plans can ensure a coordinated response during flood events, minimizing casualties and property damage (UNISDR, 2015). By adopting these strategies, Asante Mampong can build long-term resilience and mitigate the negative social and economic impacts of flooding on the community.

Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the impact of climate change on the Asante Mampong community. Despite facing numerous challenges, such as youth unemployment and increased flood risk, the community has demonstrated remarkable resilience and a commitment to addressing these issues through collaborative, community-driven efforts. Notably, the study highlights the community's proactive involvement in shaping climate change policies through regional initiatives and partnerships with the government. The research identified several key adaptation needs such as the urgency of flood risk management strategies as extreme weather events become more frequent. To enhance the community's overall resilience in the face of climate change, this study recommends addressing youth unemployment through local job development initiatives. Based on the findings, the research recommends integrating flood risk assessments into urban planning decisions as a crucial step for long-term sustainability. By implementing the community-based strategies identified in this research, such as traditional irrigation techniques, floodplain farming practices, and traditional fire management techniques, Asante Mampong can become a model for climate change adaptation in Ghana. The study recommends future research explore the effectiveness of these strategies in mitigating the impacts of climate change and fostering long-term community resilience.

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